

Managing Time Table and its Effect on Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary School Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between managing time table and its effect on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State. The study utilized correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of all 2200 students and 850 teachers in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State during the 2022/2023 academic year. The sample size of 150 teachers and 250 students were selected for the study making a total of 400 respondents. A purposive random sampling technique was used to select the sample size. The research instruments used in the study were Managing Time Table Questionnaire and Effects of Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was established by administering the instrument on 30 respondents who were not part of the actual study. The scores obtained from this pilot group were subjected to a test of internal consistency using Cronbachs' alpha reliability analysis. An overall alpha value of 0.82 and 0.74 were obtained for the study, The data collected from the instruments was analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result obtained from the data analysis revealed that there is a significant relationship between managing time table and its effect on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State. The researchers recommended that principals and teachers should effectively manage consolidated timetable to enhance students academic performance in both public and private schools and teachers should utilize teachers-wise time table in order to enhance students' academic performance in both public and private schools.

Keyword: Managing, timetabling, organization, students' academics and performance

Introduction

The impact of time table and its effect on students' academic performance has been a topical issue over the years due to its significance in teaching and learning process. School timetable is a calendar that coordinates teachers and students within the classrooms and time periods of the school day. Time table is a kind of schedule that shows when specific events will take place in a formal school setting. Chinyama and Innocent (2019) stated that time table is a plan which shows at what time certain activities supposed to take place in a school system. Time table is a reference documents created by educational professionals that clearly shows how schools resources, such as teachers and classrooms fit together with student schedules as well as with days of the week. According to Grafiati, (2021). Time table coordinates other factors including the class subjects and the type of classrooms available in the school organization.

Since the 1970s, researchers in operations research and management science have developed computerized solutions for the school timetable problem which has the potential to enhance student' academic performance. Time tabling is the act of scheduling events to happen at a particular time, and it is the present participle of time table. Michael, (2019) stated that time tabling involves deciding when events or activities will take place in time table but does not involve assigning duties to the teachers. The organization of a good timetable is such that important subjects and subjects that require calculations are best taught in the morning hours. Timetable also ensure that teachers time period do not clash and it help teachers to modify lesson plan. Ellen (2021) stated that timetable prevent wastage of time and energy and ensures equitable distribution of time and helps in the formation of good time habits. According to Brown (2018) managing timetable is the administrator ability and capability to manage timetable effectively and efficiently. Therefore, a timetable is very useful in planning ahead for the actualization of the school goals and objectives. Timetable tells the order in which events will take place; it is for managing school-related activities. It is useful for students, teachers, classrooms and other resources in order to attain educational purposes. A school timetable usually cycles every week and covers all subjects and activities that are to be carried out in a term or semester. Nwonkwo (2023) stated that timetable ensures equal distribution of time among activities and subjects.

Ellen (2021) stated that timetable is an organizational tool used to achieve clear overview of future events and a framework that lets individuals see specific activities lined up for the purpose of achieving educational goals and objectives. In this framework, it shows the time allotment among several tasks and courses. It helps the individuals who want to keep a time of their commitments. Jones (2017) stated that organization benefits when time table is properly implemented. A timetable can be applied to the whole institution, per department, per year level, or even per individual class in a school setting. It helps these groups track their upcoming activities or subjects. It specifies the kinds of projects, programme, and other activities that the school needs to fulfill. The need and importance of school timetable are emphasized in their benefits. Below are some of the essential things that a school timetable can do for the attainment of educational goals and objectives, it gives administrators, teachers, parents and students a clear picture of what is happening in the classroom at any given time, it assist in minimizing school resources such as classroom availability, teachers availability and teaching aid availability.

The need and importance of school timetable mainly revolve around time management as it allows the organization to distribute or allocate their time equally or fairly. It is used to plan the whole school academic session, including the programmes and helps school staff in allocating the number of months or days to a specific activity.

Efinila, (2018). This means that teachers need to divide the school year into four equal periods to give way to equal opportunities of learning per grading. A timetable would help teachers visualize the time given and time allocated per periodic grading. In a classroom setting, a timetable can be used to distribute time on a daily basis. This way, different subjects per grade level can be studied equally. It also helps avoid time overlapping for the subject's teachers and others classroom activities. According to Efinila (2018), effective managing of timetable helps in planning what

students will learn in order to achieve academic success because academic success is a product of effective and efficient teaching and learning process.

According to Brown (2018) management of time table organization includes not only planning what students will learn, but how they will learn it. Effective management of time table organization includes both short-term and long-term goals, and for students with exceptionalities, it addresses the goals on their individualized education programmes. Instructional planning is an important way for teachers to strategically decide what their students will learn and how they will learn it.

Wang, (2013) stated that managing time table is a factor that uses different strategies to meet various needs of all students for effective academic performance. Franklyn, (2021) opined that a well-designed school timetable helps students and teachers to understand the goals of instructional objectives, allows the teacher to translate the curriculum into learning activities and hence improves students' academic performance. Management of time table organization is a process of deciding what to teach and how to teach during the teaching-learning process. Effective management of time table helps the teacher to construct goals and objectives to enhance students' academic performance.

Managing time tabling organization is a systematic planning that helps in developing, evaluating, and managing the instructional process during the classroom process to improve students' academic performance. According to Amos (2022) effective management of time tabling organization helps to establish a positive classroom environment, make the classroom a pleasant and friendly place for effective learning to take place. It enables teachers' to accept individual differences and learning activities to be cooperative and supportive in order to enhance students' academic performance. Effective management of time tabling organization also help teachers to create a non-threatening learning environment which in turn help to enhance students; academic performance. Obani (2020), managing time tabling plays a pivotal role in organizing physical space; eliminate situations that may be dangerous or disruptive, establish classroom rules and procedures and consistently reinforce them to enhance students' academic performance.

The teacher plans instruction based on time table in order to realize the set objectives to enhance students' academic performance. Various considerations underline the process of managing time tabling organization that the teacher uses to achieve educational objectives. These are mainly - what is going to be taught and who is going to be taught. The basic purpose behind teaching is to match the subject matter with the abilities of students to enable them to realize the learning outcomes. A large number of teaching strategies are available to the teacher for achieving the desired objectives. The teacher tries to select the most suitable one with respect to the resources available to him. A teacher, therefore, has to consider all these issues while planning instruction for teaching and learning to take place in the classroom. The main issues that need to be considered during managing time tabling organization because it is a planning stage are writing of lesson note, identification and organization of content, specification of method, strategies and techniques. When time table are properly organize and plan, it go ahead to enhance students' academic performance (David, 2018).

Students' academic achievements are academic ability of students in school subject as determined by result of examination or test given. The extent of students' achievement in different subjects may be determined by the grades a student earn for a particular period of learning. Academic performance is one of the key concepts in this study. This is because academic performance enable students and parents to know the current academic state of their students; and it determines the failure and success of an academic institution (Abdullah, 2019). Academic performance are important outcomes of social studies in secondary schools (Moorezam, 2022). The performance of students in secondary schools regarding managing time tabling organization is one of the major responsibilities of every teacher with effective as this will help to improve students' academic performance. The school timetable has defined period lengths. It also has specific subjects for each period. Hence, it allows administrators to distribute enough resources to most curriculum parts. The organization of a good timetable is such that important subjects are at the best times. A timetable informs students about the time of class periods. Furthermore, it also lets them know the duration of each class period. Without a school timetable, the students will not be able to prepare properly.

Jones (2017) stated that school timetable consists of a list of the complete set of offered courses, as well as the time and place of each course offered. The purposes of the school timetable are to inform teachers when he or she is going to teach, because, and it enables students to enroll in a subset of courses without schedule conflicts. Therefore, school time table has to be prepared in-line with the principles of allocating subjects according to the number of teaching staff and area of their specialization so that a teacher cannot teach two courses in the same time slot, no classroom can be used by two courses simultaneously and each teacher has a set of unavailable teaching timeslots.

A good school timetable reduces confusion for teachers and makes students to prepare for lessons. A school timetable allows teachers to properly make their lesson notes, adequately prepare his or her class and feel comfortable. David, (2019) above all, the most important reason is developing a routine; this routine is for all students and teachers. Teachers must develop routines for students. Administrators must describe when and where students go for class. Also, administrators should tell which teacher will teach what class. A good timetable gives responsibility to teachers according to the areas of subject specialization and does not allow teachers to teach more than two classes.

These major benefits of the timetables, increases the efficient of organizational activities in the school as it predicts routine for students, teachers and other staff. The timetable helps organization to spread all activities to different units in the organization, timetable reduces confusion to a minimal level. It increased the overall efficiency of the school. The same timetable communicates to parents about what is happening in the school hours and will help parents to guide their children at home. Through predictable routines, the students and teachers perform better as they will reduce the cognitive load in planning school activities because routines have been proven to be enhancing cognition abilities. There are several types of time tables which are as follows: class-wise time table, extra curriculum time table, homework time table, consolidated time table and teachers-wise time table

Consolidated Timetable is an integral time table of all the classes in a school system. It is universal in nature and regarded as holistic in the sense that all other time table emanated from it. It contains teachers' daily work. Teachers' wise time table is specifically designed only for teachers use, it helps teachers to maintain a healthy work balance by strategically allocating time for planning, grading and professional developments. It helps educators to borne out stress and ensure they have time for personal and family commitment. Additionally, a well-structured teachers' wise time table promotes collaboration and teamwork among teachers by aligning schedules and creating designated planning period. It makes educators to come together to share resources, discuss strategies and support one another in their professional growth. It is used for the teachers because it indicates where the teachers will teach the subject and the level. It also indicates teachers non-academic duties.

Based on this background, the present study intends to investigate the relationship between managing time table and its effect on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed by the researchers that over the years students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State has been poor and not been realized. The researcher envisages that this poor academic performance of students in secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State could be attributed to inability of teachers to meet the specific learning needs of the individual students. A visit to some public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State shows that school time table has been mismanage leading to students' poor academic performance. This becomes the major problem of this study. The researchers suggests that if consolidated timetable which is an integrated timetable of all the classes in the school system, and it is universal in nature and regarded as holistic in the sense that all other timetable emanated from it while teachers-wise timetable is a designed timetable that allows teachers to allocate time for different subjects, activities and break, ensuring a balanced and productive learning experience for students and it helps teachers to establish routines and expectations, which are crucial for classroom management. Consolidated and teachers-wise timetables, if fully be implemented and utilized can improve students' academic performance.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between managing time table and its effect on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. determine the relationship between consolidated timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State
- ii. determine the relationship between teacher-wise timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between consolidated timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State
- ii. What is the relationship between teacher-wise timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between consolidated timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between teacher-wise timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Research Method

This study utilized correlational research design to determine the relationship between managing time table and its effect on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State. The target population of the study consisted of all 2200 students and 850 teachers making it a total of 3050 population in public secondary school in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State during the 2022/2023 academic year. The sample size of 150 teachers and 250 students were selected for the study making a total of 400 respondents. A purposive random sampling technique was used to select this sample size. The research instruments used in this study were Managing Time Table Questionnaire (MTTQ) and its Effects on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (ESAPQ). The reliability of the instruments were established by administering the instrument on 30 respondents who were not part of the actual study. The scores obtained from this pilot group were subjected to a test of internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis and overall alpha value of 0.82 and 0.74 were obtained which deemed adequate for the study. The data collected from the instruments was analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and tested at 0.5 level of significance.

Results

The result of this study is presented based on research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between consolidated timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of Relationship between Consolidated Timetable and Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State

Variables	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-cal	Decision
	Σy	Σy^2			
Consolidated Time Table X	112542	49383	549604	0.88	Strong Positive Relationship
Students' Academic Performance Y	222585	351715			

N=400

The result presented in Table 1 above reveals that the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.88. This shows that a strong positive relationship exists between consolidated timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between teacher-wise timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis Relationship between Teacher-Wise Timetable and Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	r-cal	Decision
Teacher-Wise Timetable X	102542	49768	150293	0.80	Strong Positive Relationship
Students' Academic Performance Y	212585	751715			

The results presented in table 2 above reveals that the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.80. This shows that a strong positive relationship exists between teachers-wise timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State.

Research Hypotheses 1:

There is no significant relationship between consolidated timetable and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Consolidated Timetable and Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Consolidated Timetable X	112542	49383	549604	0.88	0.139*	Strong Positive Relationship
Academic Performance Y	222585	241715				

*N = 400 *Significant $p < .05$; $df = 398$; critical r-value = 0.139*

The result presented in Table 3, reveals that calculated r-value of 0.88 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.139 at 398 degrees of freedom and 0.5 alpha levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that There is no significant relationship between consolidated timetable and its effect on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State was rejected. This shows that there is significant relationship between consolidated timetable

and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between teacher-wise timetable and students’ academic performance in secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State

Table 4: Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Teachers-Wise Timetable and Students’ Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State

Variables	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-cal
	Σy	Σy^2		
Teachers-time table X	102542	49768		
			150293	0.80*
Academics Performance Y	212585	751715		

*N= 400, *Significant $P < .05$, $df = 398$, critical r-value = 0.139*

The result presented in Table 4 reveals that calculated r-value of 0.80 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.139 at 398 degrees of freedom and .05 alpha levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between teacher-wise timetable and its effect on students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is retained. This shows that there is a significant relationship between teacher-wise timetable and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The result presented in Table 1, indicated that strong positive relationship exists between consolidated time table and students’ academic performance in public secondary school in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State. The corresponding hypothesis in table 3 shows that there is a strong positive relationship between consolidated time table and students’ academic performance in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Jones (2017) who opined that effect on students’ academic performance in public secondary school is significantly related to consolidated timetable. The hypothesis 1 on table 3, was strongly positive which means that there is significant relationship between consolidated timetable and students’ academic performance in public secondary school in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State.

The result presented in Table 2, indicated that strong positive relationship exist between teachers-wise timetable and effect on students’ academic performance in public secondary school in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Ellen (2021) who stated that effect on students’ academic performance in public secondary schools, is significantly related to teachers-wise timetable. The corresponding hypothesis 2 in table 4 was strongly positive which means that there is a significant relationship between teachers-wise timetable and students’ academic performance in public secondary school in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn from the study. There is an established significant relationship between managing of time table and its effect on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Education Zone, Rivers State. This is because it was revealed that consolidated timetable and teacher-wise timetable significantly relate with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ikwerre Educational Zone, Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Principals and teachers should ensure that timetable is properly managed in schools to enhance students' academic performance
- ii. Principals and teachers should ensure that duties are delegated to improve their administrative effectiveness in terms of time table management.
- iii. Seminars and workshop on effective implementation of consolidated and teachers-wise timetable should be organized by the Ministry of Education for school principals and teachers.

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